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D6.2 – Strategic Communication Plan (SCP) and Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR) – Final

Authors: **Aleksandra Jurewicz, Millaray Sierra Olea, Jana Gäbler and Nicole Heine (DECHEMA)**

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Executive Summary

The PROMISCES project, “Preventing Recalcitrant Organic Mobile Industrial chemicals for Circular Economy in the Soil-sediment-water system” is funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme. The *Strategic Communication Plan (SCP)* and *Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination (PEDR)* are part of Work Package 6: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation. Both plans together outline the project’s *Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy*, ensuring that the project consortium has a clear guideline for how to communicate and interact with external stakeholder groups.

These final plans build up on the initial Strategic Communication Plan and the initial Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (D6.1) and on the measures implemented since the initial plans early in the project. This final document presents the plans based on all materials created during the project lifetime and the expanded and refined strategies for communication, dissemination and exploitation of the project outcomes.

Specifically, the SCP and PEDR present:

- The process used to identify and analyse relevant stakeholder groups
- Communication and Dissemination channels
- Relevant journals, events, and related projects
- The individual exploitation strategies of each partner
- The role of the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN) Workshop Agreement and the Associated Partners in furthering the transfer and application of results.

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List of abbreviations

CE: Circular Economy

CEN: European Committee for Standardisation

CWA: CEN Workshop Agreement

DIN: Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V

DSF: Decision Support Framework

DWD: Drinking Water Directive

IPR: Intellectual Property Rights

KER: Key Exploitable Results

KPI: Key Performance Indicator

LCA: Life Cycle Assessment

PEDR: Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results

PFAS: Per- and polyfluoroalkyl Substances

PM(T): Persistent, Mobile and (potentially) Toxic substance

PMB: Project Management Board

SCP: Strategic Communication Plan

TMC: Technical Management Committee

WP: Work Package

WWT: Waste Water Treatment

1 Strategic Communication Plan

1.1 The context of the project

The project PROMISCES - Preventing Recalcitrant Organic Mobile Industrial chemicals for Circular Economy in the Soil-sediment-water system – is funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme to support Europe's Green Deal. PROMISCES aims at identifying i) how industrial pollution, specifically industrial persistent, mobile and potentially toxic (iPM(T)) substances, prevents the deployment of the circular economy and ii) which strategies are needed to help overcome key bottlenecks. This will directly contribute to the targets of the Sustainable Chemicals Strategy and the Zero Pollution Action Plan. This Strategic Communication Plan (SCP), complemented by the Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination (PEDR), was developed as part of work package 6 (Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation), in the aim of ensuring that the project consortium has a clear communication guideline and mission. It includes:

1. defining the communication objectives;
2. identifying the target audience;
3. establishing and engaging in communication channels to consistently deliver the key messages, i.e. online and social media presence, publications, thematic initiatives and events;
4. defining roles and responsibilities for the core communication activities;
5. outlining an assessment and monitoring plan;
6. identifying Key Exploitable Results

This final report contains the final plans build up on the initial Strategic Communication Plan and the initial Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (D6.1) and on the measures implemented since the initial plans early in the project. This final document presents the plans based on all materials created during the project lifetime and the expanded and refined strategies for communication, dissemination and exploitation of the project outcomes.

1.2 Communication objectives

The overall objective of the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities is to reach the greatest possible impact from PROMISCES and to uptake the research results by increasing the outreach and visibility of the project activities and its results. The term impact refers not only to economic or commercial aspects, but includes scientific, technical, and especially societal areas. In line with the concept of open research, open access to results will be provided for more transparency and efficiency.

Figure 1 shows the role that communication and dissemination activities play in reaching the overall objective, mainly through the establishment of targeted communication channels (see 1.5 Communication and networking activities). This means raising public awareness, engaging stakeholders, and providing transparent solutions (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Overall strategy to maximize the impact (Communication & dissemination).

Figure 2: Communication Strategy.

The communication strategy includes the dissemination and exploitation of results (e.g. transparent solutions) and will be further elaborated in the PEDR. Here, raising public awareness and engaging stakeholders are the focus, leading to the following communication objectives:

- building smart communication channels (website, social media, publications, events) to inform about the activities, benefits, and results of the project;
- interacting with stakeholder groups to identify needs and possibilities for the further dissemination and exploitation of results; and
- creating synergies with related projects and initiatives.

The SCP explains how we intend to reach these objectives by:

- presenting the core communication activities;
- defining roles and responsibilities for the communication activities;
- defining the target groups;
- providing examples for key messages regarding different stakeholders;
- creating and providing communication materials to support stakeholder engagement (logo, templates, presentations, etc.); and
- outlining monitoring and assessment of the communication activities throughout the project.

The communication and dissemination objectives and strategies presented in the SCP and PEDR have been designed to complement each other.

1.3 Identification and analysis of target and stakeholder groups

A close exchange with stakeholders right from the beginning and throughout the lifetime of the project is crucial to the project's success. This requires a comprehensive identification and analysis of potential stakeholders, which is an important component of the project. In PROMISCES, three stakeholder categories were defined:

1. PROMISCES participants (i.e. the whole consortium consisting of 27 partners);
2. Stakeholders attached to the project (External Advisory Board and associated partners); and
3. External stakeholders

Checking the pertinence of the defined target groups and refining the target-group specific communication is a constant process that requires the involvement of the PROMISCES partners with their input from their Work Packages and Case Studies. Communication topics are discussed in the monthly TMC meetings with all Work Package leaders and the feedback from the technical WPs is integrated in the communication planning.

If important stakeholder groups are missing, existing events and conferences area used to reach out to these groups. Additionally, associated partners and their networks are very important, therefore a close exchange with them will be maintained throughout the project, as well as for the uptake of results (see PEDR 2.4.5 Close cooperation with associated partners).

The following stakeholder subcategories were identified as crucial by the consortium (see Table 1), described briefly here and then further developed in terms of how to communicate to these groups in the following sections.

- i. Strategic/technical managers and practitioners in the industries related to the circular economy route, i.e. the decision-makers working in industries that need to manage the pollution they cause.
- ii. Regulators and authorities at the European, national and local scales, especially considering that a major aim of the project is to provide policy advice and to contribute to regulations.
- iii. General society as a water consumer. PROMISCES reaches out to society, especially to explain the health risks of PFAS.
- iv. The scientific community, as it can take up findings for further research and problem solving. In addition, several networks were brought up in the groups, since they can act as a multiplier for communication and dissemination activities.
- v. The knowledge and individual networks of the PROMISCES participants can be used to contact relevant external stakeholders, e.g. for sending out targeted questionnaires to explore the demands and views of stakeholders (subtask 5.1.1).

The following information was assessed early on in the Consortium and is continuously updated and re-evaluated:

- Each partner's contact information including communication channels (website, social media, newsletters) asking whether these channels can be used for PROMISCES dissemination purposes;
- Relevant events and publications for targeting stakeholders - the involvement of each partner throughout the project is continuously recorded in a "Dissemination monitoring table"; and
- Relevant networks to be used for stakeholder outreach.

Table 1: Key stakeholders per CE route

CE route	Semi-closed water cycle (A)	Wastewater reuse (B)	Nutrient recovery (C)	Material recovery (D)	Soil & groundwater remediation (E)
i. Strategic and technical managers / practitioners from related industries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wastewater utilities Drinking water companies Waterboards Chemical/pharma producers Industry producing/using PFAS/PMT Technology sector that provides remediation technologies Soil remediation companies Industry using groundwater/surface water Dredging companies/sludge treatment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Designers of new chemicals (source of pb) = Manufacturing plants, pharmaceutical firms National WWTP operators Water utilities (e.g. Veolia) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste utilities Water utilities Waterboards Chemical industry R&D/ design departments of chemical industries Organisations within a particular industry (e.g. fertilizer europe) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waterboard authorities Water utilities associations Public waste management Wastewater utilities managers Building and road construction companies Managers of public infrastructures Companies involved in dredging sediments Energy sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public water managers Drinking water companies Water agencies PFAS industries Surrounding industries Public health managers remediation specialized service companies Real estate developers Land developers Firemen Farmers Green growers Problem owners Environmental consulting companies
ii. Policy makers & regulators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> local policymakers Regulators, drinking water regulators, emissions (PMT) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Authorities Water/Health Regional Health Agencies, Catalanian 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local policymakers Politicians and ministries of finance EU regulators safety food/products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local authorities Public authorities managing sediments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local administrations Public authorities Environmental protection agencies

CE route	Semi-closed water cycle (A)	Wastewater reuse (B)	Nutrient recovery (C)	Material recovery (D)	Soil & groundwater remediation (E)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> environmental agencies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Health Department National Health Agencies Water Administration (EU, national, river basin, local) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU regulators safety fertilizers EU regulators water/soil/sediment Life cycle EU regulation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Port authorities Health agencies Environmental protection agencies Other public agencies 	
iii. General public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water consumers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Community members (end-user) NGOs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NGOs and consumers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Community members 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Citizens/civil society consumers
iv. Scientific community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Universities R&D institutes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Universities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Universities R&D institutes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> R&D institutes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> researchers
v. Networks Include associated partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nicole International Commissions for Rivers EC PMT (working group) STOWA (dutch water authorities) SEDNET IWA (micro pollutants special group meeting) Universities/research institutes H2020 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ECETOC (Centre for chemical safety assessment) EUREAU (European Federation of National Associations of Water Services) Perfluoro Council Water Europe 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainable Product Initiative (SPI) Roundtable Sustainable Chemicals ECBPI initiative SETAC IWA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Norman Network NonHazCity VEWIN - Dutch National association of water companies ESPP - European Sustainable Phosphorus Platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dechema working groups Nicole Network EUROGEOSURVEYS - European Geological surveys DBU - German association of clinical environmental medicine COMMON FORUM on Contaminated Land in Europe

CE route	Semi-closed water cycle (A)	Wastewater reuse (B)	Nutrient recovery (C)	Material recovery (D)	Soil & groundwater remediation (E)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Europe • Bank Filtration Community • European Commission (working group) • WHO • European network drinking water regulators (EndWare) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Catalan Water Partnership (CWP) • ANSES (France) • RECORD (France) • EU Phosphorus Platform 			

1.3.1 Communication aimed at strategic/ technical managers and practitioners from related industries

The term ‘related industries’ distinguishes between industries that discharge PM(T) chemicals into the environment, such as pharmaceutical firms and textile manufacturers (polluters), and industries that must deal with PFAS (control, remediate) since they rely on non-contaminated raw materials (problem owners). Most polluters are simultaneously also problem owners because they must manage the pollution they cause. Problem owners include, for example, drinking and wastewater utilities using technical processes to remove PFAS from water, dredging and soil remediation companies, building and road construction companies, and the energy sector.

Strategic managers are responsible for the long-term planning of the companies, overseeing the entire business processes and aiming to find new, effective management techniques and business designs. Technical managers deal with the application of technical solutions and are interested in new research results. Especially for the specific recommendations of the decision support framework (DSF) concerning implementation, a close exchange with both managers to get information about existing needs, problems, and solutions is indispensable.

Communication activities aimed at strategic/technical managers include measures such as:

- Presentations and the integration of stakeholder workshops into technical and zero pollution-oriented conferences and events;
- Technical and business-oriented articles in relevant magazines;
- Organizing workshops and stakeholder meetings; and
- Sending out targeted questionnaires to explore the demands and views of stakeholders.

1.3.2 Communication aimed at policy makers and regulators

PROMISCES aims to translate its zero pollution strategies into policy recommendations for relevant EU directives, strategies, and action plans. For instance, developing and testing the Decision Support Framework (DSF) within WP5 based on input from different stakeholder groups will result in insights and thus recommendations relevant for EU regulation stakeholders. Communication with policy makers and regulators is very important for maximum impact of the research results. On a regional and local scale, PROMISCES benefits from the regional networks of the partners from 9 different European countries. At the same time, some key policy actors on a regional scale, such as the Umweltbundesamt in Germany, are part of the consortium.

PROMISCES actively engages in collaboration with the five sister projects from the Green Deal Health group and also collaborates with associations such as WaterEurope or NICOLE to maximise impact in addressing policy makers.

Communication activities aimed at policy makers and regulators include:

- Presentations or sessions at high-level European water/circular economy events;
- Policy oriented articles in relevant magazines;
- Provide a policy brief on PM(T) concerns and actions in EU; and
- Taking part in the CEN Workshop (CWS) procedure and establishing a close exchange with the “Joint Group on Circular Economy (JG-CE)”.

Until now, PROMISCES has engaged in the development of two policy briefs, one as a part of the Green Deal Health Cluster together with project's sister projects ([Joint Policy Brief](#)), and the second one as an initiative from the project itself ([D5.3](#)).

1.3.3 Communication aimed at the general public

The general public is considered to be all citizens that are interested in the project and that are affected by chemical pollution (e.g. through drinking water or the food chain). Raising public awareness by explaining the wider societal relevance of the results, including the health risks of PM(T), is a core objective of PROMISCES.

Therefore, PROMISCES will develop a risk communication item for the general public (D6.3) under the leadership of partner BWB (Berliner Wasserbetriebe). This item will be a video or related online communication tool which translates the results of the project into language and terms intelligible to the general public, especially concerning risks related to drinking water consumption. Currently, BWB plans to produce two short videos, one as a general overview of PROMISCES goals and achievements, and a second one focusing on the Berlin case study (CS1).

The project website is one important platform for reaching the general public and special attention will be paid to ensuring an appealing web design and use of simple language. Another communication channel targeted at the general public is social media (LinkedIn, X) as described in 1.5 Communication and networking activities.

1.3.4 Communication aimed at the scientific community

The scientific community is an important target group since it can uptake PROMISCES results for further research and problem solving. The communication of detailed information, the quality and accuracy of the data is in the foreground.

Communication activities aimed at the scientific community will include:

- Publication of articles in relevant scientific journals;
- Organizing workshops and seminars; and
- Close collaboration with the topically related projects, especially with the sister projects ZeroPM and SCENARIOS, has been successfully established (e.g. joint organisation of events, aligning project communication channels, cooperation in the frame of the CWA). To date, several cluster meetings with the five sister projects from Green Deal topics 8.1 and 8.2 have taken place. Synergies between the projects have been assessed, the projects are in regular exchange regarding the dissemination activities. PROMISCES contributions are regularly featured in events such as workshops organized by ZeroPM and SCENARIOS and vice versa. Several joint events have been already realized.

1.3.5 Communication aimed at associations and networks

Close communication with relevant associations and networks is an important aspect of the communication strategy to transfer information and multiply impact. PROMISCES will use the connections of the consortium to reach out to these target groups. An initial list of networks that the

consortium has deemed to be relevant was included in [D6.1](#). These networks can provide advice on regulatory and technical needs and act as multipliers. For instance, the Norman network will include a section promoting the Green Deal Projects on their website.

A closer collaboration has been established with the NICOLE Network (e.g. PROMISCES final roll out event) and Water Europe (e.g., Water Knowledge Europe) for the purpose of organising sessions. Moreover, PROMISCES was also invited to participate at CWP event “Water Innovation Day” and UFZ PFAS-related event.

1.4 Communication and networking activities

After outlining the objectives, the target audience and potential key messages, the initial plan of core activities is outlined below, which consists of setting up a visual identity and several communication and dissemination channels. Information about the communication channels of all PROMISCES partners was gathered via the Communication and Dissemination Questionnaire. The input will be used for more detailed planning. The following section presents the relevance of each communication activity, its specific target audience, and its goals.

1.4.1 Visual Identity

A visual identity of PROMISCES is very important for homogenisation and branding of communication. Presentation templates, Microsoft Word templates for internal use, flyers and leaflets will always include the funding acknowledgement (Figure 3) and the PROMISCES logo (Figure 4) which is shown below. This will be made available for and deployed by the entire PROMISCES consortium via different channels and languages. Next to communication, PROMISCES visual identity will be applied in all dissemination and exploitation activities.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101036449.

Figure 3: Funding acknowledgement

Figure 4: PROMISCES logo

1.4.2 Website

The PROMISCES website (www.promiscses.eu) serves as a focal point for all the project's communication activities, and targets both the general public and an expert audience. It is a public platform for visitors to learn about the added value of PROMISCES, and to support dissemination and exploitation activities by providing the full range of information (non- and technical) related to PROMISCES and PFAS/PM(T) substances.

The website will be continuously updated with input from all partners and will raise public awareness about the risks of iPM(T)s in the environment. The section “Media Kits” provides the project's documents (e.g. flyers, logo pack, fact sheets), while the sections “Results” offers the possibility to download project results (e.g. public reports, communication items) and links to Zenodo. The section “News” provides announcements such as information about dissemination activities (seminars, meetings and conferences), the PROMISCES Blog and the recent newsletters. In the blog, the website users can read the articles from the newsletters, the interviews from the “Meet the Team” series, the “Young Researchers” series, and other interesting articles from the project such as the PFAS

Points. Also, the articles from the newsletter can be found in the blog. Under “Events”, upcoming events are shown. The section “About us” gives information concerning the partners, external stakeholders (e.g. External Advisory Board), the sister projects and related projects. Information on the project's work packages, objectives and case studies are presented in the "Project" section. Here, also the Circular Economy Routes with their respective graphics and the Online Survey Results can be viewed. In addition, there is a registration area for engaged stakeholders to become part of the PROMISCES community by subscribing to a newsletter. Through the contact form on the website, questions and requests will directly reach the project team.

The website will serve as a source of information also beyond the duration of the project. It will remain online for at least three years after the end of the project. Thus, the many information and results that can be found in the blog and in the other website sections remain.

For high visibility and dissemination, the website link and a QR-Code will be included in all communication materials.

1.4.3 Social media

Apart from the PROMISCES website, social media is a crucial and powerful tool for reaching a wider audience and disseminating project updates and important events in an easy and creative way. To this end, PROMISCES has already established a LinkedIn account <https://www.linkedin.com/company/promisces/> as it is the most widely used international professional network covering many different sectors. In addition, DECHEMA has set up a X account for also reaching citizens and non-experts. https://twitter.com/Promisces_EU DECHEMA will be responsible for creating posts and obtaining the required input from project partners.

A social media editorial plan has been set up in order to plan posts for LinkedIn and X and to get an overview of upcoming events which are relevant for PROMISCES social media channels. It is planned to post two to three times per week. In addition, a Social Media template was developed and sent to the project partners from the work packages and case studies so that the partners could identify possible topics for social media posts. Among other things, the posts cover successes, milestones (past and future), goals or the motivation of the partners. Moreover, to highlight young researchers from the PROMISCES project, a new series “Young Professionals” (e.g., PhD students and post-docs) was developed. The questions circle around the personal interest, which young professionals bring into the project and how the conducted research and new knowledge about PFAS may change their personal life and choices. This series can be found on social media and the PROMISCES blog. Furthermore, the PFAS Points offer users quick and easy information about PFAS and PROMISCES.

Figure 5: PROMISCES Young Researchers Posting

Figure 6: PFAS Points Posting

The PROMISCES LinkedIn account is very successful and reaches many people. It provides interesting topics from the project and about PFAS in general. In September 2024, the LinkedIn channel reached 1000 followers.

PROMISCES and the other projects from the Green Deal Health Cluster (ZeroPM, ALTERNATIVE, SCEANRIOS, LifeSaver and PANORAMIX) support each other on social media via liking and sharing posts. Once a month, all projects send links to the other projects with the request of liking and sharing them.

1.4.4 Project releases and materials

Dedicated materials for creating awareness and promoting project events will be created. A project flyer is currently under preparation. This should be distributed or displayed at events and the aim is to draw attention to the project and arouse curiosity. At this stage, the following materials are planned:

- A PROMISCES project poster and a short presentation slide deck introducing the project;
- Layman’s report, fact sheets;
- Project flyer;
- Materials provided by the massive open online course (MOOC) (the need for further materials will be determined during the lifetime of the project);
- Dedicated materials developed for specific occasions;
- PROMISCES roll up banner created for the final roll out event

1.4.5 Online seminars

Online seminars include a MOOC and will be targeted at young professionals and future end-users with the goal of making the scientific and regulatory community aware of PROMISCES main findings and results. Lectures for professionals will focus on PFAS/iPM(T) substances in the water, soil, and sediment cycles. Course content will range from PFAS characteristics, fate and transport in the environment, to PROMISCES technologies and management solutions. PROMISCES will provide material (PowerPoint presentations, videos of the case studies, and self-assessment study) with the project’s results. The self-study online course (6 weeks), examination and self-assessment tests will be held in English and will be available even after the project concludes. It will be shared via the TUDelft MOOC platform and will thus remain available after the project concludes.

1.4.6 Publications

Technical and scientific publications are an important channel to raise awareness about the project, foster public acceptance and disseminate information for the uptake of solutions. Table 2 and 3 show a selection of scientific journals and journals targeted at experts from policy and industry as well as magazines for the general public, which could form a channel for diffusion of PROMISCES results. The KPI targeted at the end of the project are ≥ 10 publications in peer-reviewed journals and ≥ 8 publications in technical magazines.

Table 2: Scientific journals

Name of the scientific journal
Chemical Engineering Journal
Earth System Governance
Environment International
Environmental Pollution
Environmental Science and Technology
ES&T Water
Green Chemistry
Hydrogeology Journal
Journal of cleaner production
Journal of Environmental Management
Journal of Hazardous Materials
Journal of Hydrology
Urban Water Journal
Waste Management
Water
Water International
Water Policy
Water Research

Table 3: Technical magazines

Name of the magazine	Target audience	Language
Vallès Visió	General public	Catalan
Vallès Oriental TV	General public	Catalan
Diari SOM	General public	Catalan
Nació Digital	General public	Catalan
Fundació Rivus	General public	Catalan
El Periódico Digital	General public	Catalan, Spanish
Speciality Chemicals Magazine	Fine and speciality chemicals industry	English
Freshwater Blog	General public	English
Danube Watch	Management in water pollution control	English
Le Moniteur	Construction magazine	French
Journal du Geek	New technology magazine	French
Géosciences or Géorama	Earth sciences magazine	French
Techniques Sciences et Méthodes (TSM)	Environment technology magazine	French
Actu-Environnement	Global environmental concerns (cross target)	French
Environnement Magazine	Global environmental concerns (cross target)	French
L'Usine nouvelle	Industrial, energy and chemical scopes for decision maker	French
Science et Avenir	Popular science – cross target	French
Environnement, Risques & Santé	All disciplines converging between environment and health	French
L'actualité chimique	Chemical sciences, and its relations with other sciences, industry, society and education	French
Revue Techniques Sciences Méthodes	Water and wastewater stakeholders	French
DECISIONS DURABLES	Environment	French
AEF DEVELOPPEMENT DURABLE	Environment	French
L'eau l'industrie les nuisances	Environment	French
Green Univers	Environment	French
KA (German magazine of DWA)	Management in waste and water industry	German
wwt Wasserwirtschaft Wassertechnik	Management in waste and water industry	German
GWF Wasser Abwasser	Management in waste and water industry	German
Vom Wasser	Testing laboratories; authorities; water supply and disposal companies; environmental monitoring in industry and for applied research	German
Wasserspiegel	Employees of Berliner Wasserbetriebe	German
Der Standard	Non-scientific community	German
Die Presse	Non-scientific community	German
Analytik News	Analytical laboratories	German
HyWa – Hydrologie und Wasserbewirtschaftung	Hydrology and water resources management	German
ÖWAW Fachzeitschrift	Management in waste and water industry	German, English
Ilsole24ore.com	Professionals in the technological and environmental sectors	Italian

Name of the magazine	Target audience	Language
Recycling demolizioni & riciclaggio (Edizioni PEI S.r.l.)	Industry	Italian
Servizi a rete	Professionals	Italian
Ingegneria dell'ambiente	Professionals	Italian
RETEMA	Management in environment	Spanish
La Vanguardia Digital	General public	Spanish
Aguasresiduales.info	Management in waste and water industry	Spanish
Tecnoaqua	Management in waste and water industry	Spanish
FUTURENVIRO	Environmental technologies	Spanish, English

1.4.7 Face-to-face and online events

Face-to-face, online or hybrid events are an important communication channel to reach experts, build trust, and encourage technology providers, utilities, and decision-makers to trust, promote and use PROMISCES results. The partners of the PROMISCES consortium participate in several events for networking activities to give presentations and distribute material. Additionally, PROMISCES organizes events of different formats including joint events with sister projects.

1.4.8 Additional opportunities for networking

In addition to the topics named above and the collaboration with associations and networks as important target group, the connections the consortium has established through related projects are also an important communication channel. Related projects and the respective contacts of each partner are depicted in the table below.

Table 4: Related Projects

Name of the project	Coordinator	Possible synergies & opportunities for cooperation	Contact partner within PROMISCES
ZeroPM	NGI (Stiftelsen Norges Geotekniske Institutt)	Cluster meetings, invitations to workshops/events, CENWorkshop agreement	
SCENARIOS	UPO	Cluster meetings, invitations to workshops/events, CEN Workshop agreement	
PFASTwin	HORIZON-CSA	Invitation to events	Julie Lions (BRGM)
ULTIMATE	KWR	Valorising resources within the water cycle, water and industry, joint communicating events	Ulf Mieke (KWB) Francesco Fatone (UNIVPM) (Nicole Heine, DECHEMA)
NextGen	KWR	Circular water solutions	Ulf Mieke (KWB)
IMPETUS	EURECAT	Climate change, circular economy	Hella Schwarzmüller (KWB)
FlexTreat	RWTH Aachen	Agricultural water reuse (German project)	Michael Stapf (KWB)
Life AskReach	UBA	Raising consumer awareness about substances of high concern (SVHC) in articles; improving supply chain communication processes with the aim of	Sandrine Andres (Ineris)

Name of the project	Coordinator	Possible synergies & opportunities for cooperation	Contact partner within PROMISCES
		substituting SVHC with safer alternatives; etc.	
PARC (Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals)	Anses	Task 4.2 on « Environmental and multisource monitoring » est very relevant. One aim is to “Set up the overall process of environmental and multisource monitoring in PARC with the help of a pilot study on PFAS and endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs)”	Valeria Dulio, Sandrine Andres (Ineris)
Life VERMEER	Istituto di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri IRCCS	VERMEER developed software which integrates hazard evaluation with exposure assessment for human and environment	Enrico Mombelli, Sandrine Andres (Ineris)
PROTECT	UFZ	Persistent mobile organic chemicals in the aquatic environment: Sources, occurrence and technical processes for their removal in the drinking water supply	Jochen Kuckelkorn (UBA)
TrinkWave	TU München		Dr. Thomas Track (DECHMA)
AquaNES	FH Nordwestschweiz		Dr. Alexander Sperlich (BWB) Dr. Ulf Mieke (KWB)
SOuRCE	EURECAT	Invitation to events, use of project website for communication, etc. Share of results about tech performance in PFAS removal.	Carme Bosch (EURECAT)
USETOX	UNEP/SETAC	Global consensus tool for using output for Life Cycle Impact Assessments of products and product systems	Leo Posthuma (RIVM)
Life cycle Initiative	UNEP/SETAC	Global consensus process to develop methods for output for Life Cycle Impact Assessments of products and product systems	Leo Posthuma (RIVM)
Sunshine		Work together on case study (e.g. alternatives for PFAS coatings)	Willie Peijnenburg (RIVM)
MAGO	CETAQUA	Invitation to events, sharing of information	Miren López de Alda (IDAEA-CSIC)
NATURE	CSIC	Invitation to events, sharing of information	Víctor Matamoros (IDAEA-CSIC)
FATERISK Aqua	TU Wien	Joint stakeholder workshops	Matthias Zessner / Julia Derx (TU Wien)
Danube Hazard m3c	TU Wien	Joint stakeholder workshops	Matthias Zessner
WATERUN	AIMEN	Invitation to events	FRANCESCO FATONE (UNIVPM)
ECOSEDRA	SOGEIN	Invitation to events, joined research activities	FRANCESCO FATONE (UNIVPM)
BLUE LAKES	LEGAMBIENTE	Invitation to events	FRANCESCO FATONE (UNIVPM)

Name of the project	Coordinator	Possible synergies & opportunities for cooperation	Contact partner within PROMISCES
DIGITAL WATER CITY	KWB	Invitation to events	FRANCESCO FATONE (UNIVPM)
Emerging contaminants project	CBT	Knowledge /results sharing	Josep Pascual (CBT)
Microplastics project	CBT	Knowledge / results sharing	Josep Pascual (CBT)
WATER-MINING	DELFT University of Technology	Invitation to events, results sharing, networking	Nicole Heine (DECHEMA) Josep Pascual (CBT)
Center of Competence Clean&Circle	Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski	Use of website and social networks for communication, invitation to events, etc.	Albena Varsano (Sofia University)
BioICEP	Technical University of the Shannon, Ireland	Invitation to events	Tjalf de Boer (MLS)
LIFE Capture	ABO	CEN Workshop agreement	Nicole Heine (DECHEMA)
LIFE Pristine	ACCIONA AGUA SA	Communication purposes to maximise the outreach	Aleksandra Jurewicz (DECHEMA)

1.5 Monitoring and assessment

Monitoring and assessment of the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities is an important aspect for the communication strategy. It requires a structured procedure to ensure that the right messages have reached the right stakeholders and to measure the effectiveness of the communication activities. Key performance indicators (KPIs) are used to compare the original goals with what has been achieved in the end. Suitable procedures for project-internal monitoring will be applied. PROMISCES will use the following categories to measure performance in terms of number of:

- conferences/workshops/exhibitions organized and number of attendees
- publications in peer reviewed journals with high impact factors
- publications in technical magazines
- reference documents produced
- project newsletters/ contribution to newsletters of the partners/contribution to external newsletters
- participants in project-linked seminars
- lectures linked to PROMISCES
- followers in social media channels/ social media statistics

Concrete numbers for most categories are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5: Overview of PROMISCES communication and dissemination activities and the respective KPIs

Type of dissemination (Target Audience)	Examples of targeted dissemination channels	What we want to achieve	KPI (targeted at the end of the project)
Conference / workshop / exhibitions (Policy makers, industry, public organisations & associations, utilities, researchers) Conferences	Conferences: AquaConSoil, IWA DWA, SedNet, EGU and AGU, SETAC, Aqua Urbanica, Water World Forum, World CE Forum, World Resource Forum Workshops by NICOLE, Micropol, JRC, ICPDR Exhibitions: Remtech Expo, Pollutec National expert groups: ÖWAV, French AQUAREF Parallel session at AquaConSoil	Dissemination of schemes and of PROMISCES scientific results among technical experts. Spread knowledge about novel RA approaches. Contribute to best practice documents on various topic (via ESPP, DWA, JRC). Connect local decision makers in water management with PFAS topic.	≥ 10 (by academic/research partners) workshops sessions organised by partners with minimum 20-80 participants ≥ 15 by R&I partners) proceedings / communications accepted at international conferences
Scientific journals (Researchers, industry)	Environmental Science and Technology, Environmental Pollution, Water Research, Journal of Hydrology, Journal of Cleaner, Production and others, Environment International, Water Policy, Water International, Earth System Governance	Diffusion of PROMISCES scientific results. Acceptance of PROMISCES results as part of the State of the Art	≥ 10 publications in peer reviewed journals with high impact factors
Technical magazines (Industry, researchers, general public)	Bodem, Retema, Futureenviro, KA (German magazine of DWA), Danube watch, Servizi a rete, Ingegneria dell’Ambiente, Géologues, Techniques Sciences et Méthodes, Pour la science, Industri	Diffusion of PROMISCES scientific results. Update design guidelines for advanced WW treatment. Acceptance of PROMISCES’ results as part of the State of the Art	≥ 8 publications in technical magazines

Type of dissemination (Target Audience)	Examples of targeted dissemination channels	What we want to achieve	KPI (targeted at the end of the project)
	Ambiente, Industria Química		
Reference documents (Researchers, industry, public organisations & associations)	Enhancement of existing guidelines (e.g. UBA guidelines) Contributions to national reference documents	Highlight the potential to included PFAS removal in utility planning Raise Awareness on the usage of new methods for assessment	≥ 2 reference documents
PROMISCES partners & newsletter (Researchers, public organisations and associations, industry, utilities)	Dissemination on partners' websites and newsletters. Webpage dedicated to PROMISCES (in French and English) on the institutional website of partners with pertinent links (PROMISCES website, more info, etc.)	Present PROMISCES challenges and innovations, raise awareness around the project, extend the reach of the project	Project descriptions on each partner's website ≥ 3 project newsletters ≥ 5 contributions to partners newsletters ≥ 5 contributions on external newsletters
Online webinars (Researchers, universities, industry, public organisations & associations)	MOOC on the partners' website & PROMISCES webpage Webinars PROMISCES related guestlectures at universities Young Researcher's Forum	Outreach to young professionals and future end-users to present and promote PROMISCES innovative technologies, analytical methods, monitoring concepts and advances, raise awareness of iPM(T) substances and their fate	≥ 150 participants in project-linked webinars by academic/research partner At least 1 MOOC organised by DELFLAND ≥ 5 lectures linked to PROMISCES

2 Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results

2.1 Introduction and key concepts

The Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR) complements the Strategic Communication Plan (SCP). The PEDR outlines the dissemination and exploitation objectives and strategies to ensure the greatest possible impact from the project results.

The three key concepts of this deliverable are communication, dissemination, and exploitation. While the meaning of communication is self-explanatory and its role for the project is elaborated on in the SCP, it is worth clarifying the concepts of dissemination and exploitation in terms of what they refer to and how they can be differentiated. Both terms refer to a project's results, and are defined by the Horizon 2020 programme as:

“Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights.”

(Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)

In contrast to the communication strategy, the goal of which is to reach out to and inform all identified stakeholders about the activities, benefits and impact of the project, the dissemination and exploitation strategies refer solely to the disclosure and transfer (dissemination) and uptake (exploitation) of the project results. While the dissemination channels are part of the communication channels and are therefore only briefly mentioned here, the focus of the PEDR lies on the exploitation strategy. More concretely, the EU defines exploitation as:

“.. to make use of the results produced in an EU project in further activities (other than those covered by the project, e.g., in other research activities; in developing, creating and marketing a product, process or service; in standardisation activities)”

(Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)

This requires specific exploitation routes, which form an important part of the exploitation strategy (see 1.5 Communication and networking activities).

2.2 Dissemination and Exploitation objectives

As mentioned in the SCP, the overall objectives of all the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities are to achieve the greatest possible societal impact from the PROMISCES project and to expand the uptake of the research results, by increasing the outreach and visibility of the project.

The close relationship between the project's communication and dissemination activities and their objectives can be seen in Figure 7, which specifically addresses the objectives of the three components. The communication and dissemination activities both aim to transfer knowledge and results. The defined objectives can be found in the SCP (see 1.2 Communication objectives).

Meanwhile, the exploitation objectives are more specific, aiming to:

- Foster the transfer of research results within the circular economy routes (sludge, sediments, landfill leachate, soil and groundwater remediation, municipal and industrial wastewater treatment, drinking water)
- Support the uptake of results within PROMISCES
- Ensure the uptake of results beyond PROMISCES

Figure 7: Overall strategy to maximise the impact (Exploitation)

The following two chapters outline the specific dissemination and exploitation strategies. Since the dissemination strategy has already been partly covered within the communication strategy (see SCP), the focus of the PEDR lies on the exploitation strategy.

2.3 Dissemination strategy

2.3.1 Target audience

A crucial part of the dissemination strategy is to identify the right audience and determine the appropriate key messages. Both the language and the content of the message should be considered. The SCP describes the stakeholder identification process and presents five different target audiences (see 1.3 Identification and analysis of target and stakeholder groups):

- 1) Technical and strategic managers and practitioners
- 2) Policy makers and regulators
- 3) General public
- 4) Scientific community
- 5) Associations and networks

The dissemination of results is targeted at these same groups with a special focus on practitioners, policy makers, the scientific community and networks. These groups are reached through different communication and dissemination channels.

2.3.2 Dissemination channels

Most of the same channels used for PROMISCES communication activities are also used for the dissemination activities. Important channels for distributing results include:

- Conferences, workshops and exhibitions
- Scientific journals
- Technical magazines
- Reference documents
- PROMISCES newsletter
- Online seminars

Moreover, to boost the dissemination of project results at the EU-level, PROMISCES foresees using, as applicable and available, the dissemination tools provided by the European Commission, such as Horizon Results Booster (HRB), Innovation Radar, Research and Innovation success stories, CORDIS, Horizon Results Platform and Horizon Dashboard.

Collaboration with HRB and Green Deal Support Office is established and ongoing. It has proven to be particularly helpful for implementing joint activities targeting policy makers and regulators, e.g. by preparing joint policy briefs.

2.4 Exploitation strategy

PROMISCES' exploitation strategy includes five pillars that are used to achieve the desired objectives:

- 1) Exploitation of PROMISCES innovative technologies and up-scaling roadmaps
- 2) Individual exploitation strategy for each partner
- 3) Identifying PROMISCES Key Exploitable Results and their use during and beyond the project
- 4) Transfer and application of the project results via the CEN Workshop Agreement
- 5) Close cooperation with associated partners

These pillars are elaborated in the following sections.

2.4.1 Exploitation of innovative technologies and up-scaling roadmaps

PROMISCES aims to provide smart solutions for dealing with PM(T) substances in the environment, including remediation technologies and other tools for reducing PFAS contamination. A market screening during the proposal phase identified three main markets for technologies and consulting services developed by PROMISCES: 1) water, 2) soil and groundwater remediation, and 3) recycled

fertiliser. The exploitation strategy will help ease the entry of PROMISCES developments into these markets.

Specifically, the rapid market deployment of PROMISCES outputs will be facilitated via work on two levels:

- 1) Implementation by project partners
- 2) Replication outside the consortium

Some project partners can directly implement PROMISCES results (internal end-users), although the final goal is to provide technologies and solutions for the entire EU market. The External Advisory Board will support the exploitation of results, as will the more than 34 associated partners (see 2.4.5 Close cooperation with associated partners).

2.4.1.1 Implementation by project partners

The project consortium includes all relevant actors along the innovation chain for innovative zero pollution solutions, which facilitates the fast transfer from R&D institutions to end-users. Each partner has a role in the innovation chain, from technology design and development over validation/verification and integration, to solutions, and to exploitation support. Several PROMISCES partners represent the end-user phase, providing opportunities to implement the project results directly within their organisations.

Several case studies have already identified clear implementation demands for the innovative technologies they will develop. For example, some case studies include the utility responsible for follow-up investments as a partner (BWB, CBT, DELFLAND). Since the utilities are involved from the beginning, they foresee to be able to include the project's results into their investment strategies before the project is completed.

2.4.1.2 Replication outside the consortium

The involvement of PROMISCES commercial partners, who act as technology suppliers on the market (BDS, ESOLVE, ACEA, COLAS, SIMAM, MLS and some associated partners), will strengthen the commercial exploitation of the developed technologies. Tailored exploitation plans will be generated to replicate the results outside of the consortium. Specifically, the exploitation plans will highlight the following:

- (i) Project targets
- (ii) Developed technologies/products
- (iii) Market potential
- (iv) Expected key areas of application
- (v) Customers

These plans feed into the final up-scaling roadmaps for the commercialisation of each technology (D6.8). After the case studies successfully demonstrate and validate the results of each treatment technology, including benchmarking the costs, the roadmaps will provide the basis for the up-scaling of the technologies. The roadmaps aim at outlining plans for implementation in future commercial projects.

In addition, a market analysis (D6.9) is in preparation, focussing specifically on the attractiveness, feasibility, and competitiveness of the technologies. The market study shall determine the main parameters and criteria and will contribute to a macro-analysis of the market. The most valuable and detrimental aspects for the replicability of the technologies in other EU locations will be identified.

2.4.2 Individual exploitation strategy for each partner

Through their research activities, each partner plans to increase their knowledge of iPM(T)s and their properties, fate and removal, and this information then needs to be transferred and capitalised upon. Therefore, each PROMISCES partner developed their own exploitation strategy (containing confidential data), with some outlining quantifiable targets to be reached by 2030.

Furthermore, to keep track on the innovation potential created within the project, a table “Innovation and Exploitation by WP” is being continuously updated.

2.4.3 Key Exploitable Results

The first step of building each partner’s Exploitation Strategy (2.4.2) was to define possible Key Exploitable Results (KER) of the project. To give assistance to the PROMISCES partners, WP6 (DECHEMA) developed a KER table (cf. table 6) that consists of a title for the possible KER, a description, how results can be used, potential risks/barriers for exploitation, potential users, lead partner, contributors and associated WP. This table enables the partners to narrow down the possible KER, which can be used after the project comes to an end.

Table 6: Possible Key Exploitable Results

Potential Key Exploitable Results	Description	How results can be used	Potential risks/ barriers for exploitation	Potential Users	Lead Partner	Contributors	Associated WP

Moreover, it is necessary to identify barriers and risks for exploitation and undertake appropriate measures. The barriers and risks are a regular topic for the discussions during the PMB meetings.

Based on the results from Table 6, DECHEMA conducted an interactive session during a Steering Committee meeting in November 2024 to pinpoint the most promising possible KERs and transform them into final KERs (Figure 8). PROMISCES partners contributed their ideas on how they can further exploit the results after the project ends and how they can help increase the visibility by using their networks.

PROMISCES WP6s' interactive session - from potential Key Exploitable Results to final KER

Description: this interactive session aims to narrow down the current potential KERs to final KERs.

Task:

Duration - 1h interactive session split in:

- 5 min introduction
- 15 min prioritization
- 35 min strategy discussion
- 5 closing and next steps

Figure 8: PROMISCES interactive session to identify final Key Exploitable Results.

To promote the identified final KER, they will be showcased in a dedicated space (“Exploitation Corner”) during the PROMISCES final roll out event, which takes place together with the NICOLE network (27.03-28.03.25), ensuring that the tools and technologies can be directly seen by potential industry partners and/ or potential future collaborating parties. PROMISCES SMEs and industrial partners are given the opportunity to present themselves and their results with a company booth.

A table of identified KERs, their (potential) use and potential user and stakeholder groups can be found at the end in ch. 2.5 of this deliverable.

The results of the PROMISCES project will be utilized in numerous ways to improve the management of PMT substances, with a special focus on PFAS. The application of these results is aimed at supporting the scientific community, policymakers, regulatory authorities, and industry. Final Key Exploitable Results include potential contributions to

- **Standardization and Regulation:**
 - The developed analytical methods for PFAS and other fluorinated compounds will be incorporated into technical guidance and recommendations for monitoring PFAS under the recast Drinking Water Directive (DWD).
 - The findings will be contributed to standardization efforts at CEN and DIN (German Institute for Standardization).
 - New data on the occurrence and risks of PMTs will help update regulations such as the Water Reuse Regulation and the Watch List under the Water Framework Directive.
- **Science and Research:**
 - The developed methods, such as those for trace analysis of PMTs in water and food, and bioassays for risk assessment, are reproducible and will be made available to other scientists and laboratories.
 - Models designed to simulate the behavior and transport of PFAS in the environment (e.g., in soil, groundwater, and rivers) will be accessible to the scientific community.
- **Practical Application for Water Suppliers and Industry:**

- Water suppliers and plant operators can utilize the new, cost-effective analytical methods and passive samplers for routine monitoring of water resources.
- The developed treatment and remediation technologies for PFAS-contaminated water and soil, such as the "E-Peroxone" strategy or thermal solutions, can be integrated into existing and new facilities.
- A "DSF Substitution portal" will be available to economic operators to support them in replacing hazardous substances.
- **Policy Advice and Risk Assessment:**
 - The models for assessing human health and environmental exposure and risk will serve as a foundation for policy decisions.
 - A "CEN Workshop Agreement" summarizes best practices and solutions for managing PMT substances, serving as a public guidance document that has the potential to be developed into a formal standard.

In summary, the project's outcomes will see wide application, ranging from enhancing analytical detection capabilities and developing new remediation technologies to directly supporting the creation of future environmental standards and regulations.

To ensure the exploitation, transfer and replication of PROMISCES results and to maximise the impact beyond the project's lifetime, specifically the CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) on "Soil-sediment-water system - Solutions to deal with PMT/vPvM substances" (D6.11) can be considered a great platform to discuss project results with different stakeholders (including the sister projects), synthesize results and formulate key messages for future standardisation. This supports the overall exploitation of PROMISCES results and increases the impact beyond the project duration.

The CEN Workshop is open for the direct participation of all parties interested in the development of the agreement. Hence, both relevant stakeholders (e.g., decision makers, academics, municipal and industrial actors) and civil society within and beyond Europe were encouraged to contribute to the CWA. Furthermore, two sister projects, ZeroPM and SCENARIOS, were invited to participate and present their aims and topics of concern and are included in the draft process.

The resulting CWA will represent the consensus of the involved stakeholders, as the document will be prepared collaboratively. The integrative approach will support broad acceptance in civil society and expert communities. Once completed, the CWA will be made accessible (open access) via the CEN and the EU standardisation bodies and will be valid for three years.

Although the CWA does not have the status of a European Standard, future standardisation needs will be included in the PROMISCES CWA. Future standardisation of zero pollution CE strategies is crucial for ensuring transferability, as well as application, interoperability, and replication both within Europe and internationally.

The CWA document is collaborative work, with six online meetings held. The kick off meeting for this task took place on 15th February 2024 and outlined the workshop's aim: defining optimal practices, solutions, and guidelines for managing PMT/vPvM substances. These solutions were categorized into areas of Prevention/Substitution, Monitoring, Risk-assessment, Measures/Remediation, and Prioritization for Remediation Goals. As part of the categorized solutions, a special focus is placed on the following five circular economy routes: semi-closed water cycle for drinking water supply,

wastewater reuse for agricultural irrigation, nutrient and energy recovery from treated sludge for fertilisers, material recovery from dredged sediment for eco-materials, and groundwater and soil remediation to protect water cycle.

Leadership roles for the CWA were confirmed, with Dr. Thomas Track (DECHEMA) as Chair, Dr. Veronika Zhiteneva (KWB) as Vice-Chair, and Dr. Madlen Schmudde (DIN) as Secretary. An online survey was made available so that participating members identified their categories of interest within the CWA and registered in core teams for each solution category (SC). Finally, the Chair appointed team leaders for each SC: Sarah Hale (TZW) for Prevention/Substitution, Veronika Zhiteneva (KWB) for Measures/Remediation, Hans Peter Arp (NGI) for Prioritization for Remediation Goals, Anne Togola (BRGM) for Monitoring, and Martine Bakker (RIVM) for Risk-Assessment.

At the beginning of April, all officially registered participants (40) were granted access to a SharePoint folder where they can work on the CWA document in parallel. Finally, at least 10 of the participants are external to the PROMISCES project, fulfilling KPI 6.4 (KPI 6.4: Number of project external stakeholders included in the CEN workshop agreement for the co-creation of the DS. Target: 5-15). To highlight the importance of this document, it is important to mention that also another European project ARAGORN contributed to the work.

All CWA meetings have taken place, and the official work with the participants concluded on January 29. Small changes, such as adjusting the chapter titles, have been made. Currently, the CEN Workshop Agreement is under revision by the Workshop Secretariat (DIN). Its publication is planned for March 2025. It will be made available to the public on the official CEN-CENELEC website. PROMISCES will disseminate the publication via PROMISCES social media and the website. Moreover, the participants are encouraged to promote the document within their networks.

2.4.4 Close cooperation with associated partners

Not only will PROMISCES improve the innovation capabilities of its partners and introduce them to new or larger markets, but numerous other entities (listed below), interested in high performance and competitive innovations, also support and will benefit from PROMISCES. These associated partners (APs) have stated their interest either via a letter of support (LoS) or by accepting an External Advisory Board position. Table 7 outlines how PROMISCES will capitalise on its extensive AP network to broaden the exploitation of its innovations.

The APs supported via the following activities during the project lifetime:

- Consult on up-scaling potential and market entry;
- Provisional installation/experiments with innovations, model testing and referral of other water utilities;
- Advise on technology development, uptake of regulatory tools, market, regulatory needs and considerations;
- Foster connection with academia;
- Advise on uptake of regulatory tools;
- Lobby for (new) national policies; and
- Provide deeper understanding of circular economy considerations

After the project is completed, the continued support of the exploitation activities by the APs is foreseen, such as:

- Supporting the potential market entry of technologies;
- Applying the solutions within industry;
- Conducting subsequent research collaborations;
- Supporting the uptake of regulatory and decision-support tools and new national policies; and
- Recommending other public authorities for subsequent collaborations.

Table 7: Overview of associated partners and exploitation ambitions

Category	Associated partners (AP)	Exploitation destination & timeline
Technical and industrial innovations	VEOLIA, MEWT, WAPULEC LTD, GRAFORCE, GCI, VIVA SERVIZI, WITTEVEEN+BOS, MAWV, DANONE	During: Consultation on upscaling potential and market entry After: Potential market entry of technologies, application in industry
Water utilities and agencies	CATALAN WATER AGENCY, VIENNA, WATER, ASPMA, PORT OF DUNKIRK, Alto trevigiano servizi spa	During: Provisional installation/experiments with PROMISCES' innovations, testing F&T models, referral of other water utilities After: Subsequent research collaboration or implementation of PROMISCES' innovations
Research and development	BGS, CRCCARE, TU DELFT	During: Technical advice on technology development, connection with academia After: Subsequent research collaboration
Public authorities	L'Agence de la transition écologique (ADEME) (FR), L'Office français de la biodiversité (OFB) (FR), Senatsverwaltung für Umwelt, Verkehr und Klimaschutz - Berlin (Sen UVK) (DE)	During: Advice on uptake of regulatory tools, lobbying for new (national) policies After: Uptake of regulatory and decision-support tools, new national policies, referral of other public authorities for subsequent collaboration
NGOs	CAN, ICPRD, BUND	During: Deeper understanding of CE considerations After: Subsequent collaboration
Sectors and networks	NICOLE Network, NORMAN, WATER EUROPE, WATER REUSE EUROPE, SEDNET, IAWD, VEWIN, ESPP, EUROGEOSURVEYS, DBU, COMMON FORUM	During: Advise on technical, market, lobbying, regulatory needs and considerations After: Subsequent research collaboration

2.5 Plans for post-project dissemination and use of results

As a lot of work was finalized in the last months of the PROMISCES project, thus, dissemination and exploitation of these results will evidently proceed after project end. On top of further collaboration between the partners and, cooperation with the associated partners as laid out above, each partner institution has defined a strategy for the use of results, complementing the definition of the Key Exploitable Results and their potential uses.

In addition, PROMISCES plays an important educational role by raising awareness about pollution and the circular economy. It offers capacity-building activities through open-access training,

webinars, social media campaigns, and educational resources such as MOOCs, the videos produced by BWB and consensus-based documents (CWA). These efforts target a broad audience, including local authorities, water managers, students, young professionals, civil society, and environmental NGOs, contributing to the development of a more informed, active, and resilient population.

The focus of post-project dissemination lies on dissemination of results at events, by publications, further communication and networking activities as detailed further below. For enhancing the impact of the PROMISCES policy brief and policy recommendations in D5.8 «Modular recommendations for evaluation and implementation of relevant EU directives, strategies and action plans» a specific dissemination strategy has been devised.

2.5.1 Dissemination of PROMISCES outcomes at conferences and events

PROMISCES partners keep on disseminating project results at numerous national, European and international conferences, workshops and networking events, targeting various stakeholder groups such as the scientific and technical community, industry and policy stakeholders.

Below are a few examples of events where PROMISCES partners present the project outcomes after project lifetime:

- SETAC Europe 35th Annual Meeting, 11-15/05/2025, Vienna, Austria
- Groundwater Quality, 10-13/06/2025, Bordeaux, France
- AquaConSoil 2025, 16-20/06/2025, Liège, Belgium
- Österreichischer PFAS-Tag, PFAS in der Wasserversorgung, Abwasserwirtschaft und Abfallwirtschaft, 24/06/2025, Vienna, Austria
- International Conference on CHEMICAL AND PROCESS ENGINEERING, 29/06/25-02/07/25, Florence, Italy
- RemTech Europe, 15-19/09/2025, Ferrara, Italy
- Aqua Urbanica, 21-23/09/2025, Rapperswil, Switzerland
- ZeroPM workshop „Achieving Zero Pollution of Persistent and Mobile Substances”, 7-8/10/2025, Mytilene, Greece
- Dioxin 2025, 1-6/11/2025, Antalya, Turkey
- An event to present the PROMISCES CWA to several standardization committees and expert groups is in planning by DIN (Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V., German Standardization Institute) and DECHEMA for 2026, date and venue tbd.

2.5.2 Publications

After PROMISCES' lifetime, partners' efforts to disseminate the technical project outcomes and engage with the scientific community are ongoing.

Several further articles in peer-reviewed journals have been published between April and October 2025:

- *Presence of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances in untreated leachate from regional municipal waste landfills: A first assessment for Bulgaria*
Journal of Ecological Engineering, 2025, 26(7), 93–105

- Irina Ribarova, Dobril Valchev, Gioia Valentina, Alessandro Frugis
- *Investigating the extent of PFAS contamination in the Upper Danube Basin across environmental compartments*
Environmental Sciences Europe Volume 37, Article number: 99 (2025)
Meiqi Liu, Ernis Saracevic, Thomas J. Oudega, Ali A. A. Obeid, Zsuzsanna Nagy-Kovács, Balázs László, Steffen Kittlaus, Ottavia Zoboli, Jörg Krampe, Julia Derx & Matthias Zessner
 - *Effect of Hydrophobic Cross-Linkers in Strong Base Gel-Type Resins on the Adsorption Kinetics and Capacity for Perfluoroalkyl Substances*
ACS EST Water 2025, 5, 8, 4435–4447
Florian Junge, Fiona E. Rückbeil, Regina Gnirss, Rainer Haag, Alejandro Lorente, Fabio Lorenz, Sunil P. M. Menacherry, Aki S. Ruhl, Alexander Sperlich, Ana Zidar, Olaf Wagner
 - *Plasma-assisted reduction of toxicity of landfill leachate, spiked with PFOA*
Journal of Water Process Engineering, Volume 76, August 2025, 108190
Mihaela Kirilova, Yovana Todorova, Plamena Marinova, Todor Bogdanov, Ivaylo Yotinov, Irina Schneider, Nora Dinova, Yana Topalova, Evgenia Benova

More than ten additional papers have either been already submitted to peer-reviewed journals or are still in preparation, including topics on

- PROMISCES modelling results related to WP2 and Case study 2 (Danube case)
- Technologies and results related to WP1 and Case study 1 (Berlin case)
- Further results from WP1 and WP4
- Results from WP5 co-creation workshop
- Policy recommendations (WP5)

2.5.3 Dedicated dissemination of policy related results

To ensure maximum efficiency and impact of the PROMISCES policy recommendations defined in D5.8, a number of planned dissemination activities were compiled and assigned to partners. A two-page flyer summarizing the policy recommendations for easier access and for promotion of the full deliverable was developed during the project and distributed at the PROMISCES final event for the first time.

Four of the nine recommendations were included in the PROMISCES response to the draft of the EU Water Resilience Strategy. The D5.8 summary flyer was distributed at the Water Resilience Strategy stakeholder consultation meeting in Brussels.

In addition to promoting them via social media channels and on the project website, PROMISCES policy recommendations have directly been distributed to EC officials (DG ENV) in July 2025, including participants to the WaterProjectEurope event co-organized by PROMISCES in Brussels in December 2024.

D5.8 has also been shared with several other European projects, including the five other projects of the Health project cluster as well as project UPWATER. Distribution to EurEau (European Federation of National Associations of Water Services) is equally part of the plan.

Common Forum expressed interest in organizing an event about the recommendations in D5.8, the discussion is ongoing.

Two publications, one on the policy recommendations and one on the outcomes of the co-creation workshops are currently in preparation by the WP5 partners. Drafts are already available, submission is planned before the end of 2025.

Furthermore, the policy brief and the policy recommendations were promoted within the GD-SO newsletter.

2.5.4 Communication, Networking and other activities

The PROMISCES LinkedIn channel remains operational after project end. In addition to sharing news, the pFAS points series was completed as well as a series highlighting the results of all case studies. The LinkedIn channel is also a good tool to continue collaborating with the sister projects ZeroPM and SCENARIOS which are still running. PROMISCES partners continue to deliver contributions to events organized by them.

Using EC services to boost the outreach, an articles on PROMISCES results were published on [CORDIS](#) (September 2025) and one on the GD-SO newsletter (October 2025), highlighting major results like the DSF, the policy recommendations and the CWA.

PROMISCES was asked to support a study on PFAS contamination and transfer pathways in the river Elbe catchment areas on behalf of the River Basin Community Elbe (<https://www.fgg-elbe.de/fgg-elbe-en.html>) consisting of all regions in Germany that the river Elbe or rivers that feed into the Elbe pass through, involving the German national as well as several regional governments. As this includes the Berlin area, KWB was able to confirm that in the frame of CS1 relevant measurements took place and the data will be shared for this purpose.

2.6 Annex: Table of PROMISCES Key Exploitable Results

Key Exploitable Result (KER)	Description	How results can be used	Potential Users
Analytical methods for global measurement of PFAS and other fluorinated compounds	Analytical methods developed by TOP assay in waters and solid, AOf for waters and EOF/TOF for solid	Concrete feedback and contribution/recommendations on the applicability of methods in the ongoing normalisation actions and Interlaboratory Trial organisation. Contribution on the Technical Guidelines regarding methods for monitoring PFAS under the recast DWD Contributions to: CEN TC 444 WG3 (EOF), POLMO program - (organisation of ILT). Transfer to CEN standardisation.	All laboratories, regulations for new prescriptions of monitoring; Revision of directives
Analytical methods for targeted PFAS	Analytical methods developed for targeted PFAS in water and in effluent	Concrete feedback and contribution/recommendations on the applicability of methods in the ongoing normalisation actions and Interlaboratory Trial organisation. Contribution on the Technical Guidelines regarding methods for monitoring PFAS under the recast DWD Contributions to: WG2 (target analysis for soils and sludge); POLMO program - (organisation of ILT). Transfer to DIN and CEN standardisation.	All laboratories, regulations for new prescriptions of monitoring; Revision of directives
Analytical methods for targeted PFAS	Analytical methods developed for targeted PFAS in complex matrices (e.g leachate and biochar/bio-oil by pyrolysis treatment)	Concrete feedback and contribution/recommendations on the applicability of cost-effective methods extendable to various complex matrices for routine analysis	All laboratories for routine monitoring
Analytical methods: Target analytical methods for PMTs in water and lettuce	New methods for analysis of target PMTs with focus on industrial chemicals in water and lettuce	Methods reproducible by other scientists/analysts. Methods of interest to water managers and regulators and plant operators (contracts already signed by CSIC).	Scientific community, laboratories, water managers, WWTP operators, industries, policy makers
In vitro biotest battery for risk assessment of PFAS	Cell-based bioassays for fast and sensitive testing of water samples to detect possible effects of PFAS in drinking water	Risk assessment of complex water samples in the drinking water catchment area or directly in the drinking water	Risk assessors, water suppliers, regulators

Workflows for suspect and non-target screening of PMTs in water followed by prioritization	New tools for identification and prioritization of PMTs in environmental matrices	Methods reproducible by other scientists/analysts to identify site-specific pollutants of concern in their areas of study. Tools of interest also to regulators and water managers (contracts already signed by CSIC).	Scientific community, laboratories, water managers, WWTP operators, policy makers
Demonstration of passive sampler implementation for PFAs monitoring in water	Different passive samplers tested and refined	Passive samplers as supportive method for monitoring of urban pathways (e.g. groundwater or indirect discharge)	Water authorities, water utilities
Aquatic persistence dashboard in SimpleBox model	The SimpleBox – Aquatic Persistence Dashboard (SB-AP Dashboard) has been developed as a new tool to study the extent to which PMT substances persist in water bodies as a function of their chemical substance properties and emission distribution over different water bodies.	The output of the tool gives the aquatic persistence of the organic chemical in water bodies. This is an indication of the mobility of a chemical and the likelihood that it will end up in oceans.	Risk assessors for PMT substances
Guidance Document on Emission-, fate- and transport modeling for exposure assessment of surface and groundwater	Gives guidance (D2.4) for the application of model trains for emissions, fate, transport and exposure for PMTs in the environment, which specific focus on global models, soil – groundwater interaction and the catchment– river – river bank filtration – drinking water transport route	It provides guidance for applications of models with specific focus on model trains. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • tiered approach • part of risk assessment • best use of specific models in model trains • best combination of model trains • modeling limitations of model trains Stakeholders to be addressed <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • industries, utilities, environmental authorities, and consultancies to use models • decision makers and regulators -> policy implications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industries, utilities, NGOs environmental authorities, consultancies and researchers to use models • Decision makers and regulators

<p>Generic approach for deriving soil risk limits in compliance with groundwater criteria</p>	<p>This model is for prediction of leaching of chemicals from the soil surface to groundwater. The numerical models to be used for the modelling of vertical transport (Hydrus 1D) and lateral transport have been parameterized for two scenarios: 1)) Shallow groundwater tables combined with emissions to surface water. 2) Deeper groundwater bodies combined with drinking water extraction. Risk limits for PFAS for surface water and groundwater in compliance with the proposals for the EU groundwater directive and the SCHEER have been adopted in the model. These values have been used to calculate corresponding soil concentrations.</p>	<p>The modelling approach can be adopted by risk assessors to a specific locale, e.g. a country or a catchment area. In line with the sample calculations, risk limits tailored to a specific situation can be derived</p>	<p>Risk assessors for PMT substances</p>
<p>Human Health Exposure Assessment model</p>	<p>The HHEA model is a probabilistic tool developed to evaluate the exposure for humans in 4 circular economy (CE) routes investigated in 6 of the 7 case studies in the project PROMISCES. The HHEA was applied to the following routes: 1) semi-closed drinking water cycle; 2) groundwater remediation; 3) water reuse for agricultural irrigation; and 4) nutrient recovery.</p>	<p>Exposure assessments can be performed with the tool for the routes described in the previous column.</p>	<p>Utilities, environmental authorities, consultancies, decision makers and regulators</p>
<p>In silico models for physico-chemical properties of PFAS</p>	<p>Web application for predicting Sw, VP, LogP, BCF of PFAS</p>	<p>The web-application can be used to predict 4 physico-chemical properties of PFAS.</p>	<p>Risk assessors</p>
<p>New <i>in silico</i> similarity tools other than QSPR/QSAR for identification of PM(T) properties, and new AI/ML approaches focusing on grouping approaches.</p>	<p>A model has been developed that predicts the aquatic toxicity of organic chemicals including PFAS.</p>	<p>Aquatic toxicity can be predicted based on the chemical structure of the PFAS</p>	<p>Risk assessors</p>

<p>A new model train simulating fate and transport of PFAS from soil to groundwater from contaminated site scale to catchment-scale</p>	<p>A model train based on coupling 1D models simulating water flow and reactive solute transport in soil and unsaturated zone (Hydrus 1D) with a 3D groundwater flow and transport models (MODFLOW/MT3DMS)</p>	<p>Assessment of PFAS plume in soil, unsaturated and groundwater, PFAS residence time according to land use, geological, hydrogeological, hydrological and soil and climate context</p>	<p>Industries, stakeholders, environmental authorities, policy makers, Research institutes, NGOs</p>
<p>Python-based model train</p>	<p>A model train based on coupling of PhydruS and FloPy. PhydruS runs HYDRUS-1D unsaturated zone model. FloPy is the Python package that allows to create, run and post-process MODFLOW-based models. Using both models allows to consider PFAS transport from its release point at the soil surface, travelling towards the unsaturated and saturated zones towards an exfiltration surface water body.</p>	<p>In this case, linear absorption has been assumed the main process driving PFAS transport in the subsoil. Moreover, the groundwater level is assumed to be static, thus, effect of drying and rewatering in PFAS transport is neglected. These, of course, are strong simplifications of the PFAS behaviour in the subsurface. Therefore, this approach may only be used for a first approximation of the PFAS fate and transport, especially useful when the data available is limited.</p>	<p>Industries, stakeholders, environmental authorities, policy makers, Research institutes, NGOs</p>

<p>Small- and large-scale 3D numerical (iMOD/MT3DMS) models</p>	<p>The 3D physically distributed transport models are modelled with MODFLOW 2005 and MT3DMS, implemented in iMOD-WQ (iMOD Water Quality). MT3DMS uses the flow field as calculated by MODFLOW and calculates the reactive PFAS transport along this flow field, which allows for transient simulation. For employing the 3D transport modelling approach at the larger scale, a regional groundwater flow model of the entire Danube island of Szentendre in Budapest was constructed in iMOD. This regional groundwater flow model provides the data basis as well as the boundary conditions for the two local cut-out models (the actual bank filtration models) located at the two monitored sites (Tahi and Surany), which were further calibrated on water levels in the monitoring wells at both sites. The small-scale Vienna model was constructed without a separate regional model.</p>	<p>The three models are used to study the reactive PFAS transport during the bank filtration process using the RCT package within iMOD-WQ, which allows for one-site non-equilibrium sorption. A daily time-step was implemented for the groundwater flow model. For the reference period, normally distributed daily PFAS concentrations in the Danube River were generated on the basis of statistical data from the monitoring period (minimum, mean, standard deviation, maximum) using the Python-command <code>np.random.normal</code> (Harris et al., 2020).</p>	<p>Industries, stakeholders, environmental authorities, policy makers, Research institutes, NGOs</p>
<p>Generic bank filtration model</p>	<p>This Generic bank filtration model is designed as a tool for the initial assessment of PMTs including PFAS contamination at riverbank filtrate sites. The model was developed using an analytical equation for solute transport in porous media. The one-dimensional analytical solution accounts for advection, dispersion, linear isothermal sorption, and first-order decay as described in Bear, 1979, solution given in (West et al., 2007).</p>	<p>The model is available as an R package. Model use is demonstrated in two R markdown vignettes. The first demonstrates a generic riverbank filtrate scenario, and another presents results from Promisces case study 2 data. It is possible to run your own model simply using the package functions, or by altering parameter values in the vignette itself. The code can be applied to any fate and transport problem fitting at least two criteria: (1) long-term exposure, and (2) travel times of the bank filtrate are known.</p>	<p>Industries, stakeholders, environmental authorities, policy makers, Research institutes, NGOs</p>

<p>Emission model in an urban context</p>	<p>The emission model is a tool developed specifically for urban catchments to calculate the loads of specific substances - such as PFAS and PMT - entering surface waters. This model uses measured and /or literature data to determine monthly substance loads. It focuses on three main pathways of urban water systems: stormwater discharges from separate sewer systems, effluent from wastewater treatment plants and combined sewer overflows. The model's calculations are based on data with a monthly resolution, allowing detailed temporal analysis of substance emissions. By integrating hydrological and chemical data sets, the model estimates the quantities of pollutants discharged to surface waters, providing valuable insights into the contribution of each pathway.</p>	<p>The outputs of the model include both the total monthly discharge volumes and the corresponding pollutant loads to watercourses, broken down by source (stormwater or wastewater) and pathway (separate sewer system, CSO or WWTP effluent). The results are summarized in a list in R and can be exported in various file formats, such as csv or Excel tables. Primary applications include identification of main pollution sources, uncertainty analysis, temporal and spatial analysis, urban drainage and infrastructure planning.</p>	<p>Industries, stakeholders, environmental authorities, policy makers, Research institutes, NGOs</p>
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<p>DELWAQ/SOLUTIONS model</p>	<p>The DELWAQ model is a general software program that is used to simulate water quality in a wide variety of situations, both with respect to the type of water system and to the type of water quality issues. As such the program solves coupled advection-diffusion-reaction equations using the finite volume approach.</p> <p>For the urban context two different schematisations were devised:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A network of channels and lakes to model the Berlin surface water system. • A 1D vertical schematisation to represent the lake "Flughafensee", which is a more or less separate lake in Berlin with no significant connections to the rest of the surface waters, but with noticeable discharges from surrounding activities. 	<p>The surface water system is first modelled via a hydrodynamic or hydraulic program that has been developed in close cooperation with the water quality program. In this case, the most important step was the estimation of the loads from the various wastewater treatment plants and the incorporation into the set-up for water quality calculations. The water system was schematised on the basis of the pre-existing water balance model. In a complex water system like that of Berlin where actually data on water quality are scarce, it is advantageous to have a tool that can be adapted to the situation with relatively little effort. The model suite was applied to a more or less generic PFAS type, as no information was available on the actual compounds. Also, the water system has a short residence time, which means that for such persistent substances as PFAS the accumulation in the sediment layer may be the most important aspect, and not so much the presence in the water itself.</p>	<p>Industries, stakeholders, environmental authorities, policy makers, Research institutes, NGOs</p>
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<p>Modelling of Regionalized Emissions (MoRE) model</p>	<p>The model system MoRE (Modelling of Regionalized Emissions) was initially developed by the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) in cooperation with the German Federal Environment Agency. It is based on the MONERIS model system. MoRE was developed as a tool in an open-source environment for modelling substance emissions into surface waters. In the PROMISCES project the model was adapted for modelling of PFAS, which means additional emission pathways were implemented, which might be significant for PFAS and other pathways with less significance for this substance group were simplified and grouped together.</p>	<p>Due to the flexible structure of MoRE, new substances and emission pathways can be integrated at any time, provided that the necessary input data are available, and modelling can be carried out in a reasonable way. In addition, MoRE offers the possibility to modify existing calculation approaches and to test different input data sets by comparing them. For this purpose, different variants can be created. The MoRE model system is based on an Open Source PostgreSQL or SQLite database, a generic calculation engine and the MoRE Developer user interface, which can be used to read, modify and extend the contents of the database. All computations are performed by the calculation engine, which is controlled via the user interface. The modelling results can be exported as tables via the MoRE Developer user interface and the results can be used in GIS for mapping. Users can work with MoRE in two different ways: on the basis of multi-user access in a PostgreSQL database via the Internet or as a stand-alone application on the PC (SQLite version).</p>	<p>Industries, stakeholders, environmental authorities, policy makers, Research institutes, NGOs</p>
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<p>PROMISCES watershed model for PM substances (PPM) model</p>	<p>The PPM model conceptually relies on the Technical Guidance on the Preparation of an Inventory of Emissions, Discharges and Losses of Priority and Priority Hazardous Substances (European Commission (2012)). The PPM models follow the “source oriented” approach.</p> <p>The PPM was applied to a set of 10 PFAS substances. The model was implemented on a regular grid consisting of 81,217 cells (about 1500 x 1500 m). It was set up for the period 2011-2022 and runs dynamically with a timestep of 1 day. The model therefore resolves individual weather events, intra-annual differences and inter-annual differences within the simulation period.</p> <p>The PPM explicitly distinguishes the following sources: households (domestic wastewater), industry, atmospheric deposition and construction materials. In addition, a collection of unspecified urban diffuse sources was implemented as a locally elevated concentration in soils.</p>	<p>The PPM includes a dynamic fate & transport model that covers the river network. This combines the results from the hydrology model and the emissions model, and includes various processes (Deltares, 2024a; Smits and van Beek, 2013):</p>	<p>Industries, stakeholders, environmental authorities, policy makers, Research institutes, NGOs</p>
<p>On-site chemical groundwater remediation for PFAS compound removal</p>	<p>Knowledge about the application of PS+Fe(VI) and PS+nZVI for the remediation of PFAS- and OC-contaminated groundwater</p>	<p>Net settling of the fraction associated with SPM.</p>	<p>Scientific community, environmental consultancies, engineering companies, landowners, public authorities</p>
<p>PFAS contaminated groundwater treatment using on-site ultrasonic cavitation</p>	<p>Destruction of PFAS using ultrasonic cavitation for low to elevated concentrations in waters</p>	<p>Transformation of precursors of specific PM substances.</p>	<p>Scientific community, environmental consultancies, engineering companies, landowners, public authorities</p>

Soil-washing treatment to remove PFAS from dredged sediments	Definition of the technological solution and pilot design for treating		Scientific community, environmental consultancies, engineering companies, public authorities, port authority
Drinking water treatment and design tool for design of drinking water treatment trains	supportive modelling tool to optimize adsorptive treatment	The PPM fate and transport component simulates time dependent water concentrations that allowed a validation of the model by a comparison to observed in-stream concentrations.	Water utilities, scientific community
E-peroxone based electrochemical strategy for PMT degradation	Knowledge on operation conditions and pilot design of this tech to treat wastewater effluents with focus on iPMT reduction	New funding opportunities (pubic and private)	Scientific community, environmental consultancies, engineering companies, landowners, public authorities
New data on the occurrence and risk of PMTs in the water cycle and crops	Improved knowledge on input of industrial chemicals in the water cycle through WWTP effluents, and on plant uptake of industrial pollutants. New data on the environmental occurrence and risk of PMTs made published through different means (scientific publications, public repositories, open access databases)	Data of interest for mulitple stakeholders (scientists, water managers, policy makers, municipalities, farmers, citizens...) . Support to regulators for directives update (water reuse, Watch List, etc.)	Scientific community, laboratories, water managers, WWTP operators, industries, policy makers, municipalities, farmers, citicens, etc.
Novel treatment trains for adsorptive PFAS removal from drinking water with high DOM content	Pilot-scale experience with novel treatment trains	Results are directly transferable to potential large-scale applications and can help to optimize drinking water treatment	Water utilities

Thermic solution to remove PFAS from landfill leachate sludge and concentrates	Development a technological solution to reduce the PFAS in the leachate and to manage the concentrate with thermal treatment in order to obtain the complete destruction of PFAS. The new solution can be operated in the site of landfill leachate production/treatment 1) Definition of the technological solution and pilot design for treating the leachate with focus to PFAS reduction 2) Definition of the best process condition for the treatment	1) To evaluate the possibility to integrate this solution in the existent plant dedicated to th leachate treatment 2) To propose the solution for new plants 3) New funding opportunities (public and private)	Scientific community, environmental consultancies, engineering companies, leachate treatment plant operators, public authorities
DSF	Decision Support Framework for the risk management of PM(T) substances in soil, sediment and water.	Stakeholders (e.g. water utilities, chemical industry, national authorities) can use the tool to identify, prevent, monitor, assess and mitigate PM(T) substances in soil, sediment and water.	Water utilities, chemical industry, national authorities
Substitution portal (D5.2)	A website providing support to economic operators engaged in a substitution approaches. A section of the portal is dedicated to PMTs and PFAS.	The section on PMTs and PFAS will include the results of the project in relation to substitution. The site also compiles results and resources relating to the substitution of pFAS or PMTs from other sources.	Economic operators, national authorities
CEN Workshop Agreement on "Soil-sediment-water system - Solutions to deal with PMT/vPvM substances"	The CWA aims to establish best practices, solutions, and recommendations for managing PMT/vPvM substances. It provides a collection of approaches from potential preventive measures to end-of-pipe solutions. Through the CWA, our objective is to interconnect similar initiatives and external parties, ensuring credible exploitation, transferability, and replication of results. Another key objective is to maximize the impact beyond the project's duration, thereby facilitating knowledge transfer.	Public guidance document. Could potentially be developed into a standard.	NGOs, Water utilities, Manufacturers of PMT/vPvM-related products, Research Institutes